

विकसित भारत
अभियान
1947 TO 2047

8th International Conference Indian Network for Soil Contamination Research (INSCR)

& 4th International Symposium on Ciliate Biology

on Exploring the Microbial World

From Human Health to Environmental Sustainability

April 2-5, 2024 | Conference Centre, University of Delhi, INDIA

organised by

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ISME

Federation of European
Microbiological Societies

in association with

Day 1: April 03, 2024 (Wednesday)
Venue: Conference Center, Delhi University

IST (hrs)	Event
0800-0845	Registration
0845-0945	Inauguration Ceremony (Main Hall): Guest of Honour: Prof. T. Ramamurthy
0845-0900	Lamp Lighting and University Kulgeet
0900-0905	Welcome Address by the INSCR President: Prof. Rup Lal
0905-0915	Address by DU Vice-Chancellor: Prof. Yogesh Singh
0915-0925	Address by Patron: Prof. R.C. Sobti
0925-0935	Address by Guest of Honour: Prof. T. Ramamurthy
0935-0940	Address by Organizing Secretary and Introduction to Participating Institutes: Prof. Ravi Toteja
0940-0945	Abstract Book Release
0945-1015	Inaugural Lecture 1 (Main Hall) Sudesh Kumar Yadav (Director, CSIR-IHBT, Palampur) <i>"Microbes and enzymes for sustainable production of high-value products"</i>
1015-1045	Inaugural Lecture 2 (Online) Jan Roelof van der Meer (Professor, UNIL, Switzerland) <i>"Understanding interactions in soil microbial communities for the prospect of bioremediation"</i>
1045-1100	Tea Break
	Session 1: Special Session Sponsored by INSA-IUMS (Main Hall) Microbes and Infectious Disease Chairpersons: T. Ramamurthy & Sudesh Kumar Yadav
1100-1125	Keynote Lecture T. Ramamurthy (Professor, National Institute of Cholera and Enteric Diseases NICED, Kolkata) <i>"Attributes of Infectious Diseases: A cholera paradigm"</i>
1125-1145	Yogendra Singh (Director, Delhi School of Public Health, Institute of Eminence, University of Delhi) <i>"Protein Modifications: Orchestrating The Proteome To Run The Life"</i>
1145-1205	Rup Lal (INSA Senior Scientist, Acharya Narendra Dev College, DU) <i>"Amycolatopsis mediterranei: A Powerhouse for the generation of rifamycin B analogues Effective Against MDR Strains of Mycobacterium tuberculosis"</i>

1205-1225	Yogesh Shouche (Honorary Scientist, NCCS and Professor at Azim Premji University.) “”
1225-1245	Shashank Tripathi (Centre for Infectious Disease Research, Indian Institute of Science) <i>“Translating Virus-Host interaction data into antiviral modalities”</i>
1245-1305	Ankur Mutreja (Cambridge University, UK) <i>“Vibrio cholerae O139 genomes provide a clue to why it may have failed to usher in the eighth cholera pandemic”</i>
1305-1335	Plenary Lecture 1 (Main Hall) Anil Koul (Vice President, Global Public Health Discovery & Partnerships, Johnson & Johnson) “”
1335-1420	Lunch Break
1420-1445	IUMS NOC Meeting
1445-1515	Plenary Lecture 2 (Main Hall) Pinaki Sar (Professor, IIT Kharagpur, West Bengal) “”
1515-1545	Plenary Lecture 3 (Main Hall) Chris Bowler (CNRS Director of Research, IBENS, Paris) <i>“Exploring the ocean microbe multiverse with Tara Oceans”</i>
	Session 2: Special Session under the umbrella of IMiLI (International Microbiology Literacy Initiative) Microbial Literacy in Society Chairpersons: Kenneth Timmis and Rup Lal
1545-1615	Keynote Lecture Kenneth Timmis (University of Braunschweig, Germany) <i>“The microbiologist’s special duty of care for the wellbeing of humanity and the planet”</i>
1615-1645	Keynote Lecture Rup Lal (INSA Senior Scientist, Acharya Narendra Dev College, University of Delhi) <i>“Microbial Literacy Initiative for Viksit Bharat through IMiLI: Healthy Society, Environmental Protection and Global Peace”</i>
1645-1715	Terence McGenity (Professor, University of Essex, UK) “”
1715-1730	Shailly Anand (Assistant Professor, Deen Dayal Upadhyaya College, University of Delhi) <i>“Tiny But Mighty: Microbes & Sustainable Development”.</i> ”
1730-1745	Charu Dogra Rawat (Associate Professor, Ramjas College, University of Delhi) “”

1745-1800	Hira Paul Gangnegi (retd. Professor, Department of Buddhist Studies, DU) “ <i>Microbial Literacy: A viewpoint of Microbial Literacy by a society member</i> ”
1800-1815	Tea Break
1815-1900	Cultural Program followed by dinner

Day 2: 4th April, 2024 (Thursday)

IST	Event		
0900-0930	Plenary Lecture 4 (Main Hall) Kalai Mathee (Florida International University, USA) <i>“Deciphering Microbial Dynamics in Preterm Infants: An Integrative Omics Approach to Antibiotic Resistance and Replication”</i>		
	Session 3 (Main Hall) Microbes in Agriculture and Food Production <i>Chairperson: Dharam Singh & Ravi Kumar Asthana</i> <i>Co-Chair: Janmejay Pandey</i>	Session 4 (Committee Room 1) Microbes and Industrial applications <i>Chairpersons: Prashant Phale & Kashyap Kumar Dubey</i> <i>Co-Chair:</i>	Session 5 (Committee Room 2) Microbial Ecology and Environmental Impact <i>Chairperson: S.K. Barik & Nabeel Ahmed</i> <i>Co-chair: Om Prakash</i>
0930-0955	Keynote Lecture Jyoti Prakash Tamang (Professor, Sikkim University, Sikkim) <i>“Food as Medicine”</i>	Keynote Lecture Prashant Phale (Professor, IIT Bombay, Mumbai) <i>“Pseudomonas bhartica CSV86 T: an ideal host for metabolic engineering and bioremediation”</i>	Keynote Lecture S.K. Barik (Director and Professor, CSIR-NBRI, Lucknow) <i>“Two success stories of environmental microbial technology: Improving productivity of shifting cultivation and treating AMD in small-scale coalmines”</i>
0955-1015	Ravi Kumar Asthana (Professor, Banaras Hindu University, BHU) <i>“Future Prospects of Microalgae in Agriculture and Food Security”</i>	Kashyap Kumar Dubey (Professor, JNU) “”	Rajeev Kaushik (Principal Scientist, ICAR-IARI, New Delhi) <i>“Microbiology in relation to Climate change”</i>
1015-1035	Sunil Pabbi (Principal Scientist, ICAR-IARI, New Delhi) <i>“Cyanobacteria: A sustainable resource for food and organic agriculture”</i>	Suresh Kumar Dubey (Professor, Department of Botany, BHU, Varanasi) <i>“Herbicidal influence on soil biochemical parameters and microbial community in tropical rice agroecosystem”</i>	Nabeel Ahmed (Professor and Dean, Dev Bhoomi Uttarakhand University) <i>“Nanotechnology: The Tiny Revolution with Big Impacts in Science”</i>

1035-1055	Dharam Singh (CSIR-IHBT, Palampur) <i>"Lignocellulolytic Extremozymes from Indian Himalayan Niches for Industrial Applications"</i>	Arun Kumar (Scientist, CSIR-IHBT, Palampur) <i>"Decoding the virulence strategies of Rhizoctonia solani AG1-LA to engineer rice for tolerance to sheath blight disease"</i>	Naveen Gupta (Head, Department of Microbiology, Panjab University, Chandigarh) "अभाव से समाधान तक: Microbial magic for sustainable industry and environment"
1055-1115	Tea Break		
1115-1135	Minakshi Grover (ICAR-IARI) ""	Ankit Saneja (Scientist, CSIR-IHBT, Palampur) <i>"Microbial Polysaccharide-Based Oral Thin Films for Nutraceutical Delivery: A Case Study of Pullulan"</i>	Veena Pande (Professor, Kumaun University) <i>"Ectomycorrhizae: A Boon for Himalayan Environmental Management using Biotechnological Approaches"</i>
1135-1150	Janmejay Pandey (Assistant Professor, CUH, Rajasthan) <i>"A Molecular View of Biofilms formation by Plant Growth Promoting Bacteria Isolated from Arid regions of Rajasthan and their potential role in Tripartite "Plant-Microbe Interactions"</i>	Sanjukta Subudhi (Area Convener, Microbial Biofuels and Biochemicals, The Energy and Resources Institute, New Delhi) <i>"Marine Algae Biorefinery"</i>	Rajeev Singh (Associate Professor, Jamia Islamia) <i>"Assessment of microbial indoor air quality in microenvironment for health risks"</i>
1150-1205	Amit Kumar Rai (Scientist D, National Agri-Food Biotechnology Institute (NABI), Mohali) <i>"Foodomics a frontier to translate traditional fermented foods into functional foods of multifarious health benefits"</i>	Urmi Bajpai (Professor, ANDC, DU) <i>"Coevolutionary Dynamics of Microbes, AMR and Climate Change"</i>	Nirjara Singhvi (Assistant Professor, Dev Bhoomi Uttarakhand University) <i>"Unveiling Gene Co-optive evolution of LysR type transcription regulators across strains of Mycobacterial."</i>
1205-1220	Manoj Kumar (Senior Scientist, CSIR-Indian Institute of Toxicology Research) <i>"Understanding the fungal-mediated arsenic bio-transformation/ detoxification and its utilisation for reducing arsenic in crops"</i>	Rakshak Kumar (Scientist, CSIR-IHBT, Palampur) <i>"Vitamin D2 enrichment of captive cultivated Shiitake mushroom for the production of value-added products"</i>	Sanjay Kumar Gupta (Assistant Professor, Swami Shraddhanand College, DU) <i>"Soil Metaproteome: A comparative analysis of wheat rhizosphere metaproteome grown in saline and non-saline soils"</i>
1220-1235	Om Prakash (Symbiosis Center for Climate Change and Sustainability, Symbiosis International University, Pune) <i>"Anaerobic growth and drug susceptibility of versatile fungal pathogen Scedosporium apiospermum."</i>	Ashwini P (Associate Professor and Coordinator Department of Microbiology, JSS Academy of Higher Education & Research, Mysuru) <i>"Emerging Trends and Opportunities in Microbial Entrepreneurship"</i>	Junaid Jibrán Jawed (Assistant Professor, Presidency University, Kolkata) <i>"Exploring the critical factors in host immune subversion during Leishmanial pathogenesis"</i>

1235-1305	Plenary Lecture 5 (Main Hall) Anil Tripathi (Director, Institute of Science, Banaras Hindu University) <i>"Carbon source utilization ability is crucial for the rhizocompetence of a plant growth promoting rhizobacterium, Azospirillum brasilense"</i>		
1305-1325	INSCR GB Meeting		
1325-1400	Poster session + Lunch Break		
1400-1430	Plenary Lecture 6 (Main Hall) Thulani Makhalanyane (Professor at Stellenbosch University, Pretoria, South Africa) <i>"The African Microbiome Project: Insights from studying the gut microbiomes of South Africans"</i>		
	Session 6 (Main Hall) Microbial Genomics, Metagenomics and Biotechnology <i>Chairpersons: Yogendra Singh & Pratyoosh Shukla</i> <i>Co-Chairs: Mansi Verma & Helianthous Verma</i>	Session 7 (Committee Room 1) Bioinformatics in Microbial Research <i>Chairpersons: Jyoti Prakash Tamang & S.K. Dubey</i> <i>Co-Chairs: Pushp Lata and Jasvinder</i>	Research at UG/PG Colleges (Committee Room 2) <i>Chairpersons: Ravi Toteja & Hardeep Kaur</i> <i>Co-Chairs: Pooja Bhagat & Seema Makhija</i>
1430-1455	Keynote Lecture V. C. Kalia (Professor, Konkuk University, South Korea) <i>"Novel Antibacterial Strategies: Cheating Vs Killing Bacterial Pathogens"</i>	Keynote Lecture Gunjan Pandey (Senior Research Scientist, CSIRO, Australia) <i>"Novel insights into the oxidative catabolism of (+)-pinorezsinol by Pseudomonas sp. strain SG-MS2: Pathways, enzymes, and biochemical implications"</i>	Keynote Lecture Hardeep Kaur (Off. Principal & Professor, Ramjas College, DU) <i>"Research in Colleges: Opportunities and Challenges"</i>
1455-1515	Amulya Panda (Associate Director, Panacea Biotec., New Delhi) <i>"Bugs as Drugs: The Future Medicine"</i>	Baljeet Kaur (Associate Professor, Hansraj College, DU) <i>"Artificial Intelligence: Role in Biomolecule Identification"</i>	1455-1505 Sunil Srivastava (Professor, Swami Shradhanand College) <i>"Tackling Global Health Challenges like Pandemic Preparedness, Sustainability and Health Inequity by the use of Virus Like Particles and Viral Nanotechnology Platforms"</i>
1515-1535	Asha Chaubey (Senior Principal Scientist, CSIR-IIIM, Jammu) <i>"Cold deserts of NW Himalayas as untapped resource of</i>	Jasvinder Kaur (Assistant Professor, Gargi College, DU) <i>"Phylogenomics-based reclassifications in the genus</i>	

	<i>bioactive metabolites</i>	<i>Psychrobacter</i>	
1535-1555	Pratyoosh Shukla (Professor, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi) <i>“Microbial bioremediation using bio-computational approaches- perspectives and challenges”</i>	Pushp Lata (Assistant Professor, Department of Zoology, DU) <i>“Unraveling the Microbial Fabric of Manikaran: A SeqCode-Based Approach to Identify Metabolic Activities in the Hot Spring Ecosystem”</i>	
1555-1615	Anil Kumar (Staff Scientist, National Institute of Immunology) <i>“Towards understanding the anti-cancer role of gut metabolite indoxyl sulfate on colon cancer cells”</i>	Parminder Kaur (Associate Professor, SGTB Khalsa College, DU) <i>“Exploring Microalgal Potential”</i>	
1615-1635	Natesan Manickam (Chief Scientist and Professor, CSIR-Indian Institute of Toxicology Research) <i>“Biodegradation of plastics and plasticizers by diverse bacteria: Genomic insights into the metabolic pathways and biotechnological perspectives”</i>	Pooja Arora (Assistant Professor, Hansraj College, University of Delhi) <i>“Improved Prediction of IL-13-inducing Peptides through Effective Feature Selection Method and Machine Learning Classifiers”</i>	
1635-1645	Tea Break		
1645-1705	Phoebe Oldach Global Research Team Lead, Basecamp Research) <i>“Global Metagenomic Biodiscovery to Fuel Biotechnology”</i>	Helianthous Verma (Assistant Professor, Ramjas College, DU) <i>“Study of Genomic Variations of Staphylococcus aureus: A Host Specific Analysis”</i>	
1705-1725	Kosala Sirisena (University of Colombo, Sri Lanka) <i>“Ammonia Oxidizing Microorganisms in New Zealand Soils”</i>	Sinosh Skariyachan (Assistant Professor, St. Pius X College, Kerala) <i>“In silico bio-prospecting and chemoinformatics screening of potential lead molecules against multi-drug resistant WHO priority pathogens”</i>	
1725-1745	Punyasloke Bhadury (Professor, IISER, Kolkata) <i>“Exploring microbial biocomplexity in coastal ocean: the importance of time series”</i>		
1930-2000	Plenary Lecture 7 (Only Online) William B Whitman (University of Georgia, Athens)		

"Two codes of prokaryotic nomenclature: how do they become one?"

Day 3: April 05, 2022 (Friday)

Day 3: April 05, 2022 (Friday)		
IST (hrs)	Event	International Symposium on Ciliate Biology* (Committee Room 2)
		0815-0855 <i>Keynote Lecture</i> Gaytha Langlois (Professor, Bryant University, Rhode Island, USA) <i>"Ciliates in extreme environments"</i>
0900-0930	Plenary Lecture 8 (Main Hall) Brajesh Singh (Professor, Western Sydney University, Australia) “”	0900-0940 Komal Kamra (Retd. Professor, SGTB Khalsa College, DU) “”
	Session 8- Special Session Sponsored by INSA-IUMS (Main Hall) AMR and Food-Borne Pathogens <i>Chairpersons: A.A Mohamed Hatha and Dev Raj Joshi</i> <i>Co-Chair: Parminder Kaur</i>	Flash Presentation Session (Committee Room 1) Student Oral Talks <i>Chairpersons: Rajeev Singh & Ankita Dua</i> <i>Co-Chairs: Princy Hira & Nirjara Singhvi</i>
0930-0955	<i>Keynote Lecture</i> Iddya Karunasagar (Nitte (Deemed to be University), University Enclave, Medical Sciences Complex, Mangaluru) <i>"Risk assessment for foodborne antimicrobial resistance"</i>	0945-1030 Rosaura Mayén Estrada (Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico) <i>"Diversity of Mexican Symbiotic Ciliates: An Overview of its Species Richness"</i>
0955-1015	A.A Mohamed Hatha (Professor, Cochin University of Science and Technology) <i>"Emerging infectious diseases- role of ecology and technology"</i>	

1015-1035	Dev Raj Joshi (Tribhuvan University, Nepal) <i>“Circulation of antimicrobial resistance in wastewater environments”</i>			
1035-1055	Bhabatosh Das (Professor, Translational Health Science and Technology Institute) <i>“AMR of critical and high-priority bacterial pathogens”</i>		1045-1125	Alexey Potekhin (Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Biology, St Petersburg) <i>“Diversity and Dynamics of microbiomes associated with Freshwater Ciliates”</i>
1055-1115	Mansi Verma (Assistant Professor, Hansraj College, DU) <i>“Role of Viral Omics in searching drug and vaccine targets”</i>			
1115-1135	Durgesh Narain Singh (Scientific Officer, BioNEST, BHU) <i>“Analysis of high-risk pollutants in the water of the River Ganga employing meta-omic approaches”</i>			
1135-1200	Tea Break		1130-1210	Elena Sabaneyeva (Professor, Saint Petersburg State University, Russia) <i>“Symbiotic associations in ciliates: problems and perspectives”</i>
1200-1230	Plenary Lecture 9 (Main Hall) Hans H. Richnow (Ex-Professor, Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research, Germany) <i>“Multi-Element Isotope Enantiomer Fractionation and molecular biological concepts to track transformation of persistent organic contaminants in soils and plants”</i>		1215-1300	Santosh () “”
1230-1300	Plenary Lecture 10 (Main Hall) Andreas Bechthold (University of Freiburg, Germany) <i>“Production of new natural products by bridging regulatory functions”</i>			
1300-1330	Plenary Lecture 11 (Main Hall)		1315-1355	Alan Warren (Natural History Museum Cromwell Road, London)

	Jana Jass (Örebro University, Sweden) <i>"Microbes at the interface of human and environmental health"</i>		<i>"Protists are for everyone: A personal overview of knowledge dissemination and promoting public awareness"</i>
1330-1430	Poster Session + Lunch Break		1400-1440 Valentina Serra (Project Assistant, Pisa University) <i>"Next Generation Taxonomy: Ciliophora and their bacterial symbionts as a proof of concept" (Acronym: NGTax). The project, the rationale behind, and practical applications."</i>
1430-1500	Plenary Lecture 12 (Main Hall) Max Häggblom (Rutgers University, USA) <i>"Emerging Pollutants in Urban Aquatic Environments: Microbes to the Rescue"</i>		1445-1525 Jasmine
	Session 9 (Main Hall) Entrepreneurship and Innovation in Sciences <i>Chairpersons: Jitendra Kumar & Mrutyunjay Suar</i> <i>Co-Chair: Utkarsh Sood</i>	Session 10 (Committee Room 1) Women in Science <i>Chairpersons: Suraksha S. Diwan & Atya Kapley</i> <i>Co-Chair: Charu Dogra Rawat & Vartika Mathur</i>	
1500-1525	Keynote Lecture Jitendra Kumar (Managing Director, BIRAC) ""	Keynote Lecture Daman Saluja (Professor, Dr. B R Ambedkar Center for Biomedical Research, DU) <i>"Novel strategies of drug development for enhanced antimicrobial efficacy in Neisseria gonorrhoeae"</i>	
1525-1550	Keynote Lecture Mrutyunjay Suar (Director General R&D and Innovation, KIIT University) ""	Keynote Lecture Radha Prasanna (Professor, ICAR-IARI, New Delhi) <i>"Microbes as revitalizing options in protected cultivation"</i>	1530-1610 Bettina Sonntag (University of Innsbruck Research, Austria) <i>"Ciliates involved in science communication"</i>
1550-1610	Utkarsh Sood (Assistant Professor, Kirori Mal College, DU) <i>"Biomufacturing and commercialization of thermostable DNA polymerase and protease from Thermus parvatiensis"</i>	Atya Kapley (Senior Principal Scientist, CSIR-NEERI, Nagpur) <i>"Wastewater Epidemiology and its relevance in AMR"</i>	
1610-1630	Dharam Singh (CSIR-IHBT, Palampur) <i>"Biomufacturing of Industrially important L-Asparaginase from the Himalayan extremophilic bacteria"</i>	Tista Prasai Joshi (Scientist, Nepal Academy of Science and Technology, Nepal)	1615-1700 Cristina Miceli (School of Biosciences and Veterinary Medicine University of Camerino,

		<i>"Potential pathogenic bacteria in drinking water of Nepal"</i>		Italy)
1630-1650	Aditya Thakur (Dentifrice) <i>"Dentiview: Digital oral healthcare"</i>	Namrata Misra (Assistant Professor, KIIT-TBI, Bhubaneswar) «»		<i>"Transcriptomic response of the Antarctic ciliate Euplotes focardii to plastic derivatives such as Bisphenol A"</i>
1650-1710	Panel Discussion	Vartika Mathur (Professor, Sri Venkateswara College, DU) <i>"Decoding the Dynamics of Insect-Plant Interactions: Are microbes on the driver's seat?"</i>		
1710-1750	Valedictory Ceremony (Main Hall) Chief Guest: Jitendra Kumar Guest of Honor: Mrutyunjay Suar			
1710-1720	Chief Guest Address			
1720-1730	Competition Winners Announcement			
1730-1740	Concluding Remarks			
1740-1750	Vote of Thanks			